

THE IMPACT OF SOVIET RESETTLEMENT POLICIES ON THE PEOPLES OF THE NORTH CAUCASUS AND UZBEKISTAN

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ВЛИЯНИЕ СОВЕТСКОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ ПЕРЕСЕЛЕНИЯ НА НАРОДЫ СЕВЕРНОГО КАВКАЗА И УЗБЕКИСТАНА

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18228025>

ABSTRACT

The article examines the forced relocation of North Caucasian peoples to Uzbekistan in the 1930s–1950s, focusing on the fates of Chechens, Ingush, Karachays, and Balkars. It highlights the main reasons for the deportations, including the Soviet authorities' suspicions of political disloyalty, resistance to the communist regime, and links to wartime events.

Particular attention is paid to education: the absence of national teachers forced the introduction of Russian-language schooling, which became part of a broader policy of Russification and cultural assimilation.

The article also provides statistical data on the number and distribution of settlers across the USSR, with emphasis on the Uzbek SSR as a major resettlement area. The findings demonstrate especially high child mortality rates, underscoring the devastating demographic effects.

Finally, the article considers the long-term consequences of the deportations, showing how Soviet policies led to the erosion of ethnic identity and cultural traditions, leaving a lasting impact on the future development and unity of these peoples.

Key words: soviets, resettlement policy, North Caucasus, Uzbek SSR, NKVD.

АННАТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена изучению политики насильственного переселения народов Северного Кавказа в Узбекистан в 1930–1950-е годы, с акцентом на судьбах чеченцев, ингушей, карачаевцев и балкарцев. Рассматриваются основные причины депортации, включая подозрения советских властей в политической неблагонадёжности этих этнических групп, их сопротивление коммунистическому режиму и связь с военными событиями периода Второй мировой войны.

Особое внимание уделяется проблеме образования: нехватка национальных кадров привела к введению русскоязычного обучения, что стало частью широкой политики русификации и культурной ассимиляции.

Приведены статистические данные о численности и расселении переселенцев на территории СССР, при этом подчёркивается особая роль Узбекской ССР как одного из

центров размещения. Результаты исследования фиксируют особенно высокую детскую смертность, свидетельствуя о тяжёлых демографических последствиях.

В заключение рассматриваются долгосрочные социальные и культурные последствия депортаций, показано, как политика советских властей способствовала разрушению этнической идентичности и культурных традиций, оставив глубокий след в дальнейшем развитии и единстве этих народов.

Ключевые слова: советы, переселенческая политика, Северный Кавказ, Узбекское ССР, НКВД.

Forced resettlement policies in the Soviet Union were a key instrument of state control, often used to relocate ethnic groups considered politically unreliable. Among the populations most severely affected were the peoples of the North Caucasus, including Chechens, Ingush, Karachays, and Balkars. These resettlements were primarily driven by these peoples' desires for independence and their rejection of the new Soviet ideology and way of life. Furthermore, during World War II, the lands of the North Caucasus were temporarily occupied by the Germans, which increased Soviet distrust of these ethnic groups. To strengthen their control over the region, the Soviet authorities implemented a resettlement policy—one of deportation.

This article analyzes the resettlement conditions of these peoples, as well as the systemic failures that exacerbated the suffering of the displaced, as documented in official Soviet reports.

Research related to the theme of deportation is found in the works of historians N.F. Bugai[1] and V.N. Zemskov[2]. These works, however, do not fully illuminate the fates of the peoples of the North Caucasus and Uzbekistan. Our study utilizes sources such as the report from the head of the Main Camp Administration of the OGPU, M. Berman, to G.G. Yagoda, dated May 7, 1933; a letter from L. Beria to V.M. Molotov, dated June 19, 1944; the report "On the number of resettlers and special settlers registered in special settlements" from July 15, 1949, presented by Colonel V. Shiyan; a report on the demographic data of the distribution of special settlers in the Uzbek SSR in the first half of the 1950s; and the report from Major Kurochkin of the 4th department of the 3rd division of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the USSR, "On the birth and mortality rates of special settlers, as well as the number of children who reached the age of 16," dated July 28, 1951.

From the report of the head of the Main Camp Administration of the OGPU, M. Berman, to the deputy chairman of the OGPU, G.G. Yagoda, dated May 7, 1933, one can learn about the realities of the time: "Despite your repeated instructions to the OGPU Regional Representative of the North Caucasus concerning the organization and management of the trains sent to OGPU camps and labor settlements, the condition of the newly arrived trains is completely unsatisfactory. In all trains arriving from the North Caucasus, there is an exceptionally high mortality rate and incidence of diseases, predominantly typhus and acute gastrointestinal diseases.

According to the Chief of Siblag, of the 10,185 people arriving in labor settler trains No. 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, and 29 from the North Caucasus to Novosibirsk, 341 died en route, or 3.3%, including a significant number from exhaustion. The high mortality rate is explained by the following:

Criminal negligence in selecting the contingents for labor settlements, which resulted in the inclusion of sick and elderly individuals, clearly unable to survive prolonged transportation.

Failure to comply with directives to provide the resettlers with a two-month food supply. The labor settlers in these trains had no personal food reserves and were supplied with only poor-quality bread in amounts ranging from 200 to 400 grams during the journey.

The trains were not provided with hot food, and the supply of boiled water was highly unsatisfactory, with significant interruptions. The consumption of raw water led to mass outbreaks of disease.

A similar situation occurred during the transport of camp contingents from the North Caucasus. According to the Deputy Representative of the OGPU, Comrade Panin, in a train arriving from Bataysk to the Sibltag OGPU with 1,400 people, 7 bodies, 19 typhus cases, and 10 suspected typhus cases were removed during transit. In Novosibirsk, another 2 bodies and 35 typhus and suspected typhus cases were recorded. The train was dispatched from Bataysk despite protests from the train's commissar, Comrade Shumov, against loading typhus-affected contingents."^[3]

The report and related messages clearly illustrate the devastating consequences of the resettlement policy, with the deaths of several thousand resettlers, a situation that was far from isolated.

A letter from L. Beria to V.M. Molotov, dated June 19, 1944, sheds light on the Soviet government's approach to resettlement: "As part of the resettled families of Chechens, Ingush, Karachays, Balkars, and Crimean Tatars, up to 300,000 children under the age of 16 arrived in the Kazakh, Kyrgyz, and Uzbek SSRs in 1944. The special settlers were distributed in small groups in collective farms and districts, interspersed with the local population—Russian, Kazakh, Uzbek, and Kyrgyz. They live under special regime conditions (such as the prohibition of free movement outside their designated settlements). It is not possible to organize primary schools for the children of Chechens, Ingush, Karachays, Balkars, and Crimean Tatars in their native languages due to the lack of appropriate, politically reliable teaching staff. Under these circumstances, the USSR NKVD deems it advisable to conduct the education of the children of special settlers in Russian, in existing schools at their places of residence..."^[4]

This letter makes it clear that the inability to organize education in the native languages of resettlers due to the lack of "politically reliable" educators resulted in a government directive to teach these children in Russian, furthering the broader Russification policy.

According to the report "On the number of resettlers and special settlers registered in special settlements" from July 15, 1949, presented by Colonel V. Shiyan on July 16, 1949, the total number of resettled Chechens, Ingush, Karachays, and Balkars was 192,953 people, including 55,594 men, 73,346 women, and 62,013 children.^[5]

The peoples of the North Caucasus ranked second in terms of special settlers after the Germans, reflecting the Soviet government's clear stance against these peoples, their distrust of the mountaineers, and the attempt to scatter them across various parts of the country to weaken their ethnic unity and potential resistance.

The report provides detailed demographic data on the distribution of special settlers in the Uzbek SSR during the first half of the 1950s. The total number of special settlers during this period was 123,267, including 14,539 Karachays, 120 Chechens, 108 Ingush, and 249 Balkars. These groups were distributed across various regions, with the highest concentrations in Tashkent, Samarkand, and Fergana.

Distribution by Regions of the Uzbek SSR: Bukhara region – 4,745 people, including: Germans – 337; from the North Caucasus: Chechens – 12, Ingush – 33, others – 2. Kashkadarya region – 4,395 people, including: Germans – 167; from the North Caucasus: Ingush – 1. Samarkand region – 24,887 people, including: Germans – 2,625; from the North Caucasus: Karachays – 12, Chechens – 1, Ingush – 4, Balkars – 4. Tashkent region – 40,940 people, including: Germans – 1,197; from the North Caucasus: Karachays – 527, Chechens – 64, Ingush – 56, Balkars – 245, others – 4. Fergana region – 19,985 people, including: Germans – 1,026; from the North Caucasus: Ingush – 11, Chechens – 1. Khorezm region – 68 people, including: Germans – 49; from the North Caucasus: Chechens – 42. Karakalpak region – 713 people, including: Germans – 65, Kalmyks – 537; from the North Caucasus: Chechens – 42. [6]

From the report of Major Kurochkin, head of the 4th department of the 3rd division of the USSR Ministry of Internal Affairs, "On the birth and mortality rates of special settlers, as well as the number of children who reached the age of 16" dated July 28, 1951, the following information is available: in 1945, 2,230 children were born, and 44,652 died, with 1,978 children registered; in 1946, 4,971 children were born, and 15,634 died, with 4,584 children registered; in 1947, 7,204 children were born, and 10,849 died, with 7,268 children registered; in 1948, 10,348 children were born, and 15,182 died, with 16,041 children registered; in 1949, 13,831 children were born, and 10,252 died, with 15,763 children registered; in 1950, 14,973 children were born, and 8,834 died, with 14,317 children registered. From 1945 to 1950, a total of 53,557 children were born, while 104,903 died, with 59,951 children registered in total. [7]

Between 1945 and 1950, 53,557 births and 104,903 deaths were recorded. These figures starkly illustrate the scale of human loss caused by forced resettlement. Particularly alarming is the high level of child mortality, with 44,652 children dying in 1945 alone.

The Soviet resettlement policies from the 1930s to the 1950s had a profound and lasting impact on the peoples of the North Caucasus. The high mortality rates, harsh living conditions, and forced assimilation into Russian culture underscore the destructive nature of these policies. The experiences and suffering of the resettlers cannot be adequately described in words. Having lost their homes and possessions, these people wandered in foreign lands, working under appalling conditions, seeking only justice and understanding of the situation they found themselves in.

The data presented in the reports testify to the systematic disregard of the Soviet authorities for the well-being of the resettled peoples. The lack of food, medical assistance, and transportation infrastructure led to mass, preventable deaths. Furthermore, the forced imposition of the Russian language as part of the broader policy of Russification reflects a larger strategy of cultural assimilation and political control.

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